

Table S6. Short-circuit currents and electrophysiologic parameters in ALI base differentiation media. Data represent short circuit current values for baseline currents and resistance of monolayers. Amiloride inhibited ENaC currents (Δ Amil), Forskolin/IBMX stimulated cAMP currents, CFTR_{Inh-172} inhibited currents (Δ Fsk + CFTR_{Inh-172}), and ATP-activated currents (Δ ATP). Values represented are (mean $\pm$ SEM); D = Donor.

AB-ALI	Baseline currents (μA/cm²)	Resistance (Ω.cm²)	ΔAmil (μA/cm²)	ΔFsk/IBMX (μA/cm²)	ΔFsk/IBMX + CFTR_{Inh172} (μA/cm²)	ΔATP (μA/cm²)
D1	17.76 $\pm$ 1.29	319.4 $\pm$ 25.99	-6.29 $\pm$ 0.50	14.63 $\pm$ 2.28	-22.11 $\pm$ 1.77	1.07 $\pm$ 0.35
D2	22.30 $\pm$ 0.81	227.7 $\pm$ 14.24	-3.20 $\pm$ 0.64	13.63 $\pm$ 2.02	-23.97 $\pm$ 1.89	2.54 $\pm$ 0.27
D3	23.20 $\pm$ 1.129	217.3 $\pm$ 25.47	-12.21 $\pm$ 1.27	14.68 $\pm$ 0.89	-24.07 $\pm$ 0.80	4.32 $\pm$ 0.30
D4	17.50 $\pm$ 3.012	164.5 $\pm$ 29.21	-7.93 $\pm$ 0.19	13.01 $\pm$ 1.67	-14.03 $\pm$ 1.48	2.38 $\pm$ 0.30
D5	21.23 $\pm$ 2.03	140.5 $\pm$ 20.99	-10.90 $\pm$ 0.34	5.17 $\pm$ 1.22	-10.80 $\pm$ 0.50	1.12 $\pm$ 0.15